

Adsorption of Dimethoate (*O,O*-Dimethyl-*S*-(*N*-methyl)- carbamoymethyl)phosphorodithioate on some Clay Minerals and Soils

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Solution phase studies on the adsorption of dimethoate (*O,O*-dimethyl-*S*-(*N*-methyl)-carbamoymethyl)phosphorodithioate on three sodium saturated clay minerals, *i.e.* bentonite, fuller's earth, and kaolinite, and two soils, *i.e.* Kapurthala soil and Keylong soil at 15 and 25° have indicated that dimethoate is adsorbed by all the clay minerals and soils. The adsorption isotherms are L-shaped for bentonite and fuller's earth and S-shaped for kaolinite, Keylong soil and Kapurthala soil. The order of adsorption among clay minerals is found to be, bentonite > fuller's earth > kaolinite and between soils is, Keylong soil > Kapurthala soil. Adsorption of dimethoate decreases with the rise of temperature indicating the involvement of Van der Waals' forces during adsorption process. Averaged value of $\bar{G}$ (partial molar free energy) varies between 113 and 915 cal mol⁻¹ at 15 and 25°, being maximum in the case of bentonite. The data obtained satisfy Freundlich equation. The value of K is seen to be highest in case of bentonite, which indicates stronger interaction of the insecticide with the clay mineral.

THE present study is aimed at investigating the nature of adsorption of dimethoate on three clay minerals and two soils and also ascertaining the effects of various physical factors such as concentration of the pesticide, temperature and time of exposure.

Experimental

The clay minerals (bentonite, kaolinite and fuller's earth) were ground and converted to the Na form by following standard techniques. Two soil samples collected from Punjab and Himachal Pradesh were also passed through 200 mesh sieve. The soil samples have following characteristics.

Kapurthala soil (natric ustochreptic camborthids): pH 10, E.C. 1.5, O.C. 0.20, clay 19.6% (loam), sand 51.4%, silt 29.6% and C.E.C. 3.0 meq/100 g; Keylong soil (Udalfs): pH 6.9, E.C. 0.28, O.C. 0.76, clay 19.7% (silt loam), silt 48%, sand 32.2% and C.E.C. 14.5 meq/100 g.

Adsorption experiment: 100 mg of each of the oven-dry soil/clay mineral was weighed into glass stoppered reagent bottles. A stock solution of dimethoate in distilled water (200 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) was prepared. Suitable aliquots of 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10 ml were added to different bottles. The final suspension was made up to 10 ml in each case. These samples were incubated with frequent shaking for at least 24 h at 25° followed by centrifuging and the insecticide left in was examined colorimetrically¹. Similar adsorption experiments were also performed by incubating the samples at 15°.

Results and Discussion

The amounts of dimethoate adsorbed per 100 mg of adsorbent at 15 and 25° were plotted against equilibrium concentration (Figs. 1 and 2). The

Fig. 1. Adsorption isotherms for dimethoate on clay minerals: (O) 15 and (Δ) 25°.

Fig. 2. Adsorption isotherms for dimethoate on soils : (O) 15 and (Δ) 25°.

isotherms are S-shaped for kaolinite, Kapurthala and Keylong soils, while for bentonite and fuller's earth, these are of L-shaped according to the classification given by Giles *et al.*³. The S-shaped isotherms suggest that the dimethoate behaves as a monofunctional adsorbate which is adsorbed as single unit (rather than as a micelle), and that in this process it meets strong competition from the solvent molecules. Further, if dimethoate is assumed to have moderate inter-molecular attraction, the S-shaped curve suggests that in the adsorbed layer it is adsorbed vertically in a regular array.

On the other hand, if adsorption is regarded as the attachment of the bombarded solute molecules on the available vacant sites on the substrate, the initial curvature of the L-shaped isotherms may then be attributed to the difficulty that these solute molecules face to find a vacant site as more and more vacant sites on the substrate are filled. It would then suggest that either the solute is not vertically oriented or that it faces no competition from the solvent molecules in the adsorption on the soil/mineral. The adsorption of a number of herbicides on Na-montmorillonite clay by Weber⁸ and Bailey *et al.*⁴ shows L-type of isotherms.

The extent of adsorption of dimethoate on clay minerals varies in the order as, bentonite > fuller's earth > kaolinite, while in the case of soils the order is, Keylong soil > Kapurthala soil. Further, it has been observed that adsorption of dimethoate on bentonite is about 2 times as high as on kaolinite at 15°. The difference in the adsorption capacity may

be attributed to the difference in some important characteristics of adsorbent, *i.e.* structure of adsorbent, pH, surface area *etc.* Bentonite having surface area 600-800 m² g⁻¹ will show greater adsorption capacity than kaolinite (7-30 m² g⁻¹). This substantiates our results.

Kapurthala soil shows less adsorption capacity as compared to Keylong soil. The low adsorption capacity of alkaline Kapurthala soil may be attributed to the presence of weaker forces involved in the adsorption of dimethoate due to the replacement of most of the hydrogen of the carboxylic and phenolic groups⁶ of its organic matter by such ions as Na⁺ and K⁺. Due to the presence of more such ions, Kapurthala soil will have more hydrophobicity/hydrophilicity ratio which would render this soil more dispersible and have less particle contact causing a decrease in adsorption capacity. It can, thus, be concluded that low pH of the soil will favour the adsorption of dimethoate.

Dimethoate, though contains a CH₃CONH- group, remains unhydrolysed in an alkaline Kapurthala soil under the present mild experimental conditions since substituted amides get hydrolysed under very drastic conditions⁶.

Effect of temperature : The data for the adsorption of dimethoate on three clay minerals and two soils at 15 and 25° have been plotted in Figs. 1 and 2. It is seen that the amount of insecticide adsorbed on all clay mineral and soils decreases with the rise of temperature, as expected for the exothermic nature of adsorption process.

Evaluation of partial molar free energy : Bailey *et al.*⁴ have determined the partial molar free energy of macroscopically homogeneous open thermodynamic system⁷ by means of the expression :

$$-\bar{G} = RT \ln C_e/C_o$$

where, R = molar gas constant, T = absolute temperature, C_e = equilibrium concentration, and C_o = initial concentration of the dimethoate solution prior to adsorption.

The results obtained for averaged values of the partial molar free energy change ($\bar{G}$) using above relationship are recorded in Table 1. The change in this thermodynamic parameter is a measure of the extent of driving force of the process. It is clear from the results that among the clays, the average value of $\bar{G}$ is the highest for bentonite and the least for kaolinite, indicating thereby that the driving force involved in the process of adsorption of dimethoate is more in bentonite and least in kaolinite, while in case of soils, it is more for Keylong soil as compared to Kapurthala soil.

Apparent heats of adsorption : The adsorption data of dimethoate at 15 and 25° were used to calculate the apparent heat of adsorption in the manner suggested by Giles *et al.*⁹ and the results are presented in Table 2.

TABLE 1—AVERAGE $\bar{G}$ VALUES FOR DIMETHOATE ADSORBED BY CLAY MINERALS AND SOILS

Adsorbent	$-\bar{G}$ cal s mol $^{-1}$	
	15°	26°
Bentonite	914.5	640.1
Fuller's earth	758.8	684.6
Kaolinite	315.4	112.8
Keylong soil	447.5	368.8
Kapurthala soil	365.1	188.1

TABLE 2—APPARENT HEAT OF ADSORPTION OF DIMETHOATE ON CLAY MINERALS AND SOILS

Temp. = 15-25°

Adsorbent	Equilibrium concn. μ g	ΔH kcal mol $^{-1}$
Bentonite	200-600	6.87- 6.88
Fuller's earth	200-600	8.28- 6.58
Kaolinite	200-600	16.28-18.52
Keylong soil	200-600	4.93- 5.71
Kapurthala soil	200-600	11.68-13.92

The apparent heat of adsorption which is the cumulative sum of heat changes resulting from: (i) the detachment of the solute from association with solvent, and (ii) the attachment of solute to substrate, is suggestive of the operation of physical forces, such as Van der Waals' forces and hydrogen bonding during dimethoate adsorption on clay minerals and soils taken in the present investigations.

Application of Freundlich adsorption equation:

It is seen that the data obtained for the dimethoate adsorption satisfy the Freundlich equation giving straight line (Figs. 3 and 4) in each of the

Fig. 3. Freundlich adsorption isotherms of dimethoate on clay minerals at 25°: (O) bentonite, (●) fuller's earth and (Δ) kaolinite.

Fig. 4. Freundlich adsorption isotherms of dimethoate on soils at 25°: (O) Kapurthala soil and (●) Keylong soil.

adsorbents. The values of k and n for each adsorbent are presented in Table 3.

TABLE 3

	Bentonite	Fuller's earth	Kaolinite	Keylong soil	Kapurthala soil
k	252.2	218.8	54.95	117.5	58.7
n	2.89	2.59	3.03	2.60	2.96

Since the constant k is a measure of the strength of adsorption, the highest k value in the case of bentonite indicates that as compared to other clays and soils the insecticide is strongly bound with bentonite.

Degradation products: The concentrated extract of the solution, left after adsorption experiment, was analysed for breakdown products by tlc, but no degradation product could be detected.

References

1. D. A. GAJANG and M. S. SCHECHTER, *J. Agric. Food Chem.*, 1968, 11, 68.
2. C. H. GILES, T. H. MACEWAN, S. N. NAKHWA and D. SMITH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 3973.
3. J. B. WEBER, *The Amer. Mineralogist*, 1966, 51, 1657.
4. G. W. BAILEY, J. L. WHITE and T. ROTHBERG, *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. Proc.*, 1968, 32, 222.
5. H. O. BUCKMAN and N. C. BRADY, "The Nature and Properties of Soils", 7th. ed., Eurasia Publishing, New Delhi, 1971, p. 90.
6. A. I. VOGEL, "Practical Organic Chemistry", 2nd ed., Longmans Green, London, 1951, pp. 986-37.
7. K. L. BABCOCK, *Hilgardia*, 1968, 37, 525.
8. C. H. GILES, H. V. MEHTA, C. E. STEWART and R. V. R. SUBRAMANIAN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 4860.